

Hyperthermia after Epidural Analgesia in Obstetrics: Epidural-Related Maternal Fever

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ABSTRACT:

Epidural analgesia is popular labor analgesia used during delivery, epidural related maternal fever or epidural hyperthermia is a term used when laboring woman temperature increased after epidural analgesia and when other causes of fever are eliminated. Many theories established, but the most leading once are immunomodulatory effects and thermoregulation. The increase in body temperature can carries a significant adverse effect for both mother and fetus However till now there are no preventive or treatment methods towards maternal hyperthermia, or are diagnostic tool to differentiate it from maternal infection.

Keywords: Epidural analgesia, immunomodulatory, maternal hyperthermia

INTRODUCTION:

Regional techniques provide excellent analgesia with minimal depressant effects on the mother and the fetus. Epidural analgesia remains the gold standard for treating labor pain with a proven safety for both the mother and baby. Epidural hyperthermia, also known as epidural-related maternal fever (ERMF), refers to the situation in which a parturient who has an epidural for labor analgesia develops an increased body temperature. Epidural related maternal fever (ERMF) was first described in 1989 by Fusi et al in a study in which it was reported that laboring women who received epidural analgesia were more likely to experience a rise in core temperature (1C over 7 hours) than those who received intramuscular meperidine (pethidine) for labor analgesia without any evidence of clinical infection among the participants. ERMF seems to be a unique in laboring pregnant women compared to non-pregnant surgical population.

INCIDENCE OF MATERNAL HYPERTHERMIA:

Intrapartum hyperthermia is the term used for increased maternal temperature during labor. It can be due to infection or other causes like ERMF. In parturients with uncomplicated labor, body temperature increases by about 25% due to an increase in maternal metabolic rate, but this does not result in a significant increase in body temperature [1].

Hyperthermia is defined as an elevated core temperature during labor of 38°C on one occasion or 37.5°C on two consecutive occasions two hours apart. Epidural hyperthermia and intrapartum infection are the two major etiologies [2]. The incidence of intrapartum hyperthermia is 20% in parturients with epidural analgesia and 5% in those without. In parturients without epidural analgesia, intrapartum hyperthermia is almost exclusively secondary to infection. In parturients with epidural analgesia, intrapartum hyperthermia may be secondary to infection or a direct result of the epidural itself. Epidural analgesia does not increase the risk of intrapartum infection, and so approximately 75% of cases of epidural hyperthermia are caused by the

epidural. However, currently it is not possible to differentiate cases of epidural hyperthermia that are caused by intrapartum infection from cases that are a consequence of the epidural itself [3]. Many studies have demonstrated a link between epidural analgesia and maternal hyperthermia. The early studies were observational (retrospective and prospective). In addition, many randomized controlled trials consistently showed the increased risk of fever associated with the use of epidural analgesia in laboring women. According to these studies, maternal hyperthermia occurs in about 15%-25% of patients who received labor epidural analgesia [4].

MECHANISMS OF MATERNAL HYPERTHERMIA:

There are a number of hypotheses that address epidural-related hyperthermia. The most leading theories among them are immunomodulation and sympathetic block. None of them is proven but both are supported by preliminary evidence. Immunomodulatory effects of labor epidural analgesia are also called sterile inflammation.

It is postulated that epidural administration of local anesthetic during labor provokes a sterile febrile response. The onset of spontaneous labor has been found to be associated with an increased pro-inflammatory cytokine response [5]. Pro-inflammatory cytokines (e.g., interleukin IL-1, IL-6, tumor necrosis factor-alpha [TNF- α], and interferon gamma [INF- γ]) initiate immune defense against exogenous organisms, for example, by activating neutrophils.

On the other hand, anti-inflammatory cytokines (e.g., IL-1 receptor antagonist [IL-1ra], IL-4, and IL-10) antagonize the pro-inflammatory cytokines and thus reduce inflammation. Elevated levels of endogenous pro-inflammatory cytokines and placental inflammation have been measured in parturients following labor epidural analgesia [6][7].

Pregnant women with higher serum pro-inflammatory cytokine expression (e.g., IL-6), recorded at admission to hospital, are more likely to develop ERMF [8]. Local anesthetic drugs administered epidurally could increase the levels of the pro-inflammatory cytokines [9]. A randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial found that prophylactic anti-inflammatory glucocorticoids reduced ERMF in a study of 200 nulliparous women. High-dose methylprednisolone (100 mg every 4 hours) reduced ERMF incidence when compared with a low-dose regimen and placebo [10], which suggested that the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines is important in initiation of fever. The net result is that there will be an increase in pro-inflammatory cytokines and a reduction in anti-inflammatory cytokines seen in pregnant women. It seems that an inflammatory-specific feature of labor is

relevant to ERMF because maternal fever does not occur in non-laboring women who have an elective cesarean delivery under neuraxial anesthesia [11].

Sterile inflammation can be driven either by cellular injury, which acts as an initiator of sterile inflammation (endogenous molecules called alarmins that are released following tissue and mitochondrial injury) [12]. Bupivacaine absorbed from the epidural space may impair mitochondrial function [11], leading to activation of inflammation that produces pro-pyrogenic cytokines (e.g., IL-1 β and IL-18) [13], or by direct effects of local anesthetics on immune function. Local anesthetics can lead to deleterious immune effects, including reduced neutrophil mobility [14], phagocytosis [15], chemotaxis, and superoxide generation [16]. Inhibition of leukocyte function could render women more vulnerable to systemic inflammation.

A study to investigate a genetic predisposition as a risk factor for ERMF showed the relationship between genetic variations of IL-1ra, neuraxial analgesia, and cesarean delivery. Patients with genetic variation associated with high circulating levels of IL-1ra had lower cesarean delivery rates, but using neuraxial analgesia disrupted this link [17]. More studies are needed in this aspect.

The Thermoregulation/Sympathetic Blockade Hypotheses Body temperature control is dependent upon heat production and heat loss. Heat loss is regulated by two pathways of the sympathetic nervous system: the noradrenergic and the cholinergic pathways. The noradrenergic pathway is responsible for active cutaneous vasoconstriction, and the cholinergic pathway is responsible for active cutaneous vasodilation and sweating [18].

In thermoneutral conditions and during cold stress, heat loss is regulated solely by the noradrenergic pathway. However, during heat stress, heat loss is almost exclusively regulated by the cholinergic pathway. In non-pregnant individuals, epidural anesthesia blocks active vasoconstriction, which leads to cutaneous vasodilation and increased cutaneous heat loss and leads to decreased body temperature. Consequently, the effect of neuraxial blockade on body temperature is dependent upon body temperature before block placement. Before elective cesarean delivery or non-obstetric surgery, patients are in a thermoneutral state, and so neuraxial blockade blocks active vasoconstriction, resulting in increased heat loss and a reduction in body temperature [19]. By contrast, neural blockade during established hyperthermia blocks the active vasodilation and sweating, resulting in decreased heat loss [18]. Labor is a heat stress, and so it is believed that the sympathetic blockade associated with intrapartum epidural analgesia would limit heat loss. It has been demonstrated that epidural anesthesia for intrapartum

cesarean delivery limits heat loss and, as a result, body temperature increases [20].

Mechanisms for hyperthermia (a reduction in cutaneous heat loss or skin blood flow) following neuraxial blockade include:

1. limited evaporative heat loss by decreased sweating [2]
2. thermoregulatory vasoconstriction
3. baroreceptor-mediated reflex vasoconstriction (a physiological response to a reduction in mean blood pressure) [21]
4. non-thermoregulatory vasoconstriction (an elevated set-point during fever) [22]
5. blockade of active cutaneous vasodilation [18]
6. decreased heat-dissipating activities such as hyperventilation, since after effective epidural analgesia the minute ventilation will be reduced, decreasing heat dissipation and subsequently increasing body temperature [23]; these activities are common in the absence of effective labor analgesia, which, in turn, decreases heat loss.
7. reduced shivering thresholds [24]

On the other hand, studies also show minimal evidence for a central thermoregulatory-mediated cause for epidural-related maternal fever [25][26].

RISK FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH ERMF:

In general, there is limited research that has identified specific risk factors associated with ERMF. The studies done have shown different results.

The conventional epidural remains the most popular technique used in obstetric analgesia; however, other techniques may be used, such as combined spinal-epidural (CSE) or dural puncture epidural (DPE). Studies have shown an increased incidence of ERMF with CSE [27], while another study demonstrated increased incidence of fever in obstetric patients with a spinal catheter [28].

Opioids used as an augment with local anesthesia in laboring patients: a study illustrated that there was no difference in the occurrence of ERMF if analgesia was conducted with or without opioids [29].

On the other hand, a retrospective study in which they compared ropivacaine and levobupivacaine (both with 2 mg/mL fentanyl) for labor analgesia among nulliparous patients showed that levobupivacaine was associated with a higher incidence of maternal fever than ropivacaine [30].

Many studies have evaluated the effect of different concentrations of local anesthetics used for labor epidural analgesia on the incidence of ERMF. Some reported that using a lower concentration reduces the incidence of fever [31], while others showed no differences or reported conflicting results.

The maintenance of epidural analgesia in laboring women is either by continuous epidural infusion (CEI), patient-controlled epidural analgesia (PCEA), or programmed intermittent epidural boluses (PIEB). Studies showed that using CEI carried a higher rate of ERMF compared with intermittent techniques [32][33]. The majority of studies have reported that ERMF occurs within 6 hours of commencing labor epidural analgesia [34]. Several studies have therefore suggested that the development of ERMF is dependent on the duration of labor and exposure to epidural analgesia drugs [35][32].

Parity may be associated with the likelihood of development of ERMF; however, results from studies are conflicting, and this warrants further research [36].

Several RCTs investigating early vs. late epidural placement during labor have concluded that the timing of epidural placement has no impact on the incidence of maternal fever [37].

CLINICAL EFFECT OF MATERNAL HYPERTHERMIA:

On the mother:

Fever, either due to infection or noninfectious causes, is associated with hyperdynamic circulation with a high cardiac output state and leads to increased oxygen demand [38]. Besides, women who receive labor epidural analgesia were more than twice as likely to receive antibiotics postpartum [39]. Parturients with fever have an increased risk of cesarean delivery and postpartum hemorrhage, as inflammation is associated with impaired uterine contractility and increased risk of surgery [40] and therapies such as tranexamic acid and uterotonics due to the increased risk of postpartum bleeding [41]. On the other hand, intrapartum fever may also be associated with an increased need for assisted vaginal delivery [42]. More studies are needed, as until now there is no study that has established a direct link between ERMF and the risk of cesarean and operative vaginal delivery.

On the fetus:

Parturients with fever, whatever the cause, are associated with increased fetal temperature during labor [43]. Intrapartum fever (of any etiology) is associated with adverse neonatal outcomes including hypotonia, early-onset seizures, reduced Apgar scores, assisted ventilation, increased neonatal sepsis, neonatal antibiotic use, and neonatal intensive care unit admission [44]. Studies showed that maternal fever due to infection such as chorioamnionitis has an association with cerebral palsy. Besides the direct effects of infection, it is postulated that inflammation may lead to preterm birth, which impacts neurodevelopmental outcomes. Currently, there is insufficient clinical evidence or data to determine if a

direct association specifically between ERMF and neonatal brain injury exists [45].

A recent study found that labor epidural analgesia with fever is associated with an increased risk of neonatal infection, including sepsis, uncharacterized infection, and pneumonia, but not necrotizing enterocolitis [46]. However, several other studies demonstrated no connection between ERMF and increased risk of neonatal infection [47].

MANEGEMENT OF MATERNAL HYPERTHERMIA:

Fever during labor can be infectious or non-infectious. The clinical diagnosis of chorioamnionitis is done on clinical bases, while conformation of the diagnosis will be done only by histological examination of placenta post-delivery. As a result, the management will include the initiation of intrapartum antibiotic and observation of mother and the fetus, regardless the cause of fever. A proper communication between the team is very important including the anesthesiologist the obstetrician and the pediatrician. Administration of intrapartum antibiotics is recommended whenever an intraamniotic infection is suspected or confirmed. Antibiotics should be considered specifically in the setting of isolated maternal fever as often occurs with ERMF (any temperature recorded between 38C and 38.9 C with no other clinical criteria indicating intraamniotic infection and with or without persistent temperature elevation).

CONCLUSIONS:

Maternal hyperthermia is a clinical finding in women receiving epidural analgesia during labor, there are many theories about its cause, but yet no one can be confirmed as a causative factor, it can be due to the epidural procedure itself or the effect of medication used for analgesia and can be multifactorial. Hyperthermia carries adverse effect for mother and fetus but they are no enough studies linked between ERMF and its side effect on mothers or fetus. There are on currently any preventive or treatment method for ERMF, at the same time it is not easily distinguished from other cause of maternal hyperthermia. There is currently insufficient evidence to warrant a change in the recommendations regarding providing labor epidural analgesia, and the benefits of good quality labor analgesia. Further studies are always recommended.

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